

Dual-fibre solid-phase microextraction coupled with gas chromatography - mass spectrometry for the analysis of volatile compounds in traditional Chinese dry-cured ham

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Abstract

The multiple intelligent sensory technologies including the electronic nose (E-nose), electronic tongue (E-tongue), and computer vision were applied to evaluate the sensory properties of Jinhua dry-cured hams. The back propagation neural network (BPNN) models exhibited satisfying performance on simultaneously predicting different sensory attributes ($R^2 > 0.935$). The dual-fibre solid-phase microextraction (SPME) combined with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was used to analyse the volatile compounds of Jinhua dry-cured hams. The total number (72) of volatile compounds identified by the dual-fibre SPME were larger than those identified by the mono-fibre SPME method using a single fibre. The Jinhua dry-cured hams with the different storage times could successfully be distinguished based on the dual-fibre SPME. This study suggests that data fusion of multiple intelligent sensory technologies and the dual-fibre SPME are promising methods for flavour evaluation of Jinhua dry-cured hams.

Keywords: Jinhua dry-cured ham, Electronic nose, Electronic tongue, Computer vision, Dual-fibre SPME

Introduction

Chinese dry-cured hams are increasingly popular in the world because of the unique flavour. Jinhua dry-cured ham is one of the most famous dry-cured hams in the world. The traditional processing of Jinhua dry-cured ham consists of green ham preparation, salting, washing, sun-drying and shaping, ripening, and post-ripening. The sensory properties of Jinhua dry-cured hams changed significantly when the storage time increase during the post-ripening procedure [1]. The multiple intelligent sensory technologies including the electronic nose (E-nose), electronic tongue (E-tongue), and computer vision could be applied to evaluate Jinhua dry-cured hams [2]. To further explore the volatile compound profiles of Jinhua dry-cured hams, the solid-phase microextraction (SPME) fibres coated with different stationary phases could be used. The types and extraction parameters could be optimized for the implementation of dual-fibre SPME to distinguish Jinhua dry-cured hams.

Experimental

Sample preparation

Jinhua dry-cured hams were supplied by Jinhua Jinzi Ham Co., Ltd. (Jinhua, Zhejiang province, China, 119.65 E, 29.08 N). A total of 18 hams were divided into 3 groups (6 hams/group) according to the storage time (1 year, 2 years, and 3 years) that were defined as J1, J2, and J3, respectively. The *biceps femoris* muscle parts of hams were cut into cubes (1 cm×1 cm×1 cm) for the detection of computer vision. Afterwards, these cubes were ground into powder, and 10 g powder was used for E-nose detection. Finally, 5 g powder was added into 20 mL deionized water and kept still for 2 h. The centrifugation of the sample solution was performed for 30 min on the condition of 9500 r/min. The supernatants were processed through the 0.45 μm aqueous microporous membrane, and the filtrate was diluted in a ratio of 1:15. The finally obtained solution was used for E-tongue detection. The *biceps femoris* muscle was ground with a grinder. Then, 4 g of minced muscle and 7 g of distilled water saturated with NaCl were put into the 20 mL headspace vial for the detection of SPME.

Detections based on intelligent sensory technologies

The E-nose (SuperNose, Isenso Intelligent, Shanghai, China) equipped with 14 sensors, the E-tongue (Astree II, Alpha MOS Company, Toulouse, France) equipped with 7 sensors, and the computer vision system (Shenzhen Jingtuoyoucheng Technology Co., Ltd) were applied. For E-nose detection, the ham powder (10 g) was put into a 100 mL head-space vial which was sealed with the plastic wrap, and was kept still for 30 min, and the detecting time was 60 s. For E-tongue detection, the solution was put into an 80 mL glass beaker, and the detection lasted

for 120 s. The computer vision system consisted of a complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) camera (1/2.33 inch, Panasonic Electric Works, Ltd.), two light sources (natural-light LEDs, 5500 K), a zoom lens with an eyepiece lens (0.5×) and an objective lens (0.7×-4.5×), a height-adjustable platform and a soft light box (400 mm×400 mm×400 mm). All images were saved as the JPG format with a size of 640×480 pixels. Then, a 300 × 300 pixel region of interest (ROI) which focused on the centre of the original image was extracted for the following analysis. For each ham, 5 replicates were conducted, and 90 data sets (5 replicates/ham × 6 hams/category × 3 categories) were obtained from E-nose, E-tongue, and computer vision, respectively. All the experiments were conducted at the room temperature of 20 °C ± 1 °C.

Features extraction methods

The peak values of E-nose data and the signals of E-tongue at 120 s were extracted as the features for the modelling. For the computer vision data, the mean values and the standard deviations of redness (R), greenness (G), and blueness (B) were extracted from each image as the features.

Dual-SPME combined with GC-MS

50/30 µm DVB/CAR/PDMS and 85 µm Carboxen/PDMS were used as the dual-SPME. After extraction the fibre was immediately introduced into a 7890B GC coupled with a 5977A MS (Agilent technologies, CA, USA) for about 5 min in splitless mode. GC oven program was 40 °C for 2 min, ramped at 4 °C/min to 70 °C, and then ramped at 1 °C/min to 80 °C and ramped at 3 °C/min to 100 °C, ramped at 7 °C/min to 240 °C, holding for 3 min. Chromatographic separation was performed with a HP-5ms (30 m×0.25 mm I.D.×0.25 µm thickness) fused silica column from Agilent and ultra-high purity helium was used as the carrier gas. Electron-impact mass spectra was generated at 70 eV with m/z scan range from 35 to 550 amu. The ion source temperature was 230 °C [3].

Results and discussion

A total of 27 features were extracted from the intelligent sensory technologies data that could reflect different characteristics of Jinhua dry-cured hams. The response values obtained from the E-nose, E-tongue, and computer vision were shown in Figure 1. Several values such as S2, S4, S6 in E-nose, and S2 S6 in E-tongue, and R value in computer vision were significant different among the different Jinhua dry-cured hams. The results demonstrated that the intelligent sensory technologies could characterize the Jinhua dry-cured hams from different angles. Furthermore, the principal component analysis (PCA) and linear discriminant analysis (LDA) were applied to perform the dimensionality reduction and data visualization. The PCA is the unsupervised dimensionality reduction method, while the LDA is the supervised one which takes full advantage of the label information of different samples. Normally, the distribution of different sample groups in the LDA plot exhibits the larger distances among different groups and the smaller ones within one group. The two-dimension visualization plots of PCA and LDA were shown in Figure 2. The spatial distribution of sample points exhibited a clustering phenomenon of different groups. The sum of PC1 and PC2 contained 49.44% variance information of original data. The LD1 and LD2 contained almost 100% variance information. The result indicated that the LDA could classify different Jinhua dry-cured hams better than PCA. The fusion data was further used for BPNN modelling for simultaneously predicting sensory attribute results. The BPNN model exhibited good performance both in calibration set ($R^2 > 0.974$) and validation set ($R^2 > 0.935$).

Figure 1: Response values obtained from the E-nose (a), E-tongue (b), and computer vision (c).

Figure 2: PCA (a) and LDA (b) results based on the fusion data of E-nose, E-tongue, and computer vision.

The fibres of DVB/CAR/PDMS and Carboxen/PDMS were applied for the dual-fibre SPME. A total of 80 volatile compounds were identified by the dual-fibre and the mono-fibre SPME. The Venn diagram of volatile compounds identified by the dual-fibre SPME and mono-fibre SPME was shown in Figure 3. Among them, 72 volatile compounds were identified by the dual-fibre SPME, which demonstrated that the dual-fibre SPME could identify more volatile compounds than mono-fibre SPME (63 compounds by the DVB/CAR/PDMS SPME and 53 compounds by the Carboxen/PDMS SPME). In addition, a total of 14 volatile compounds were only identified by the dual-fibre SPME method, which indicated that the dual-fibre SPME method was more efficient to extract more volatile compounds in Jinhua dry-cured hams. The dual-fibre SPME method was applied to analyse the three Jinhua dry-cured hams (J1, J2 and J3), and the result was shown in Figure 4. In the following work, the correlation analysis between the dual-fibre SPME method and E-nose will be conducted to verify the superiority.

Figure 3: Venn diagram of volatile compounds identified by the dual-fibre SPME and mono-fibre SPME.

Figure 4: The types and proportions of volatile compounds identified in (a) J3, (b) J2, (c) J1 by the dual-fibre SPME method.

Conclusion

The different Jinhua dry-cured hams could be successfully classified based on the fused data of multiple intelligent sensory technologies, and the BPNN model could simultaneously predict sensory attributes scores of Jinhua dry-cured hams. The developed dual-fibre SPME method exhibited better coverage and higher extraction capacity than the conventional mono-fibre SPME.

References

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